

LITERATURE AS A TOOL FOR IMPROVING COMMUNICATION SKILLS AMONG NATIVE AND NON-NATIVE LEARNERS

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ABSTRACT: Many non-native and native speakers from throughout the world have demonstrated that English is a global language. It is also known as the global language because it is the primary means of communication across countries. In our country, the use of English as a common language is critical in education. English learners must place a major emphasis on communication skills. The ultimate purpose of language instruction is to increase communicative abilities. Pragmatics is the process of transferring meaning through communication, and language proficiency is viewed as a tool for communication. Through teaching literature there is a possibility of instilling communication skills among the learners. Pragmatic competence is the ability to perceive and transmit concepts that are more appropriate and acceptable for the cultural and social contexts in which communication occurs. Even though English is used at many levels of communication, speakers must be familiar with a wide range of pragmatic components in order to produce coherence and the ability to adapt to a number of contexts. As a result, one of the primary goals of school should be to improve pragmatic ability while simultaneously assisting with future comprehension.

Keywords: *English, communication, literature, activities, communication skills, day to day life.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Communication is a skill that enables one person to collect and communicate information to another. So, communicating in English is a skill that can only be honed via constant practice and familiarity with the target languages. This skill is useful in widening students' comprehension abilities. If a person wants to achieve his or her mission, he or she must be able to effectively communicate with others. (P. Chairat 2016). Various tactics can be employed to improve communication. Listening to literature, especially poetry, is one of the tactics. Seeing life through another person's eyes may also be beneficial. Poetry is a simple language that expresses a wide range of feelings. It brings the reader joy. It helps students develop their speaking skills. It is a tool that may be used depending on the pupils' attitude. It encourages people to express their opinions and perspectives on tough societal issues. Poetry is a vital aspect of language instruction. Poetry is the actual substance that enhances the student's comprehension of the language they are striving to learn. The researcher's primary goal is to improve students' verbal communication skills by teaching poetry in the classroom. (M. D. Mehra 2013).

In today's highly competitive business world, one of every college's primary tasks is to prepare students for future employment in a changing labor market. To put it another way, for students to compete for graduate positions, academic institutions must appropriately prepare and train them, especially with the spread of mass higher education (HE) and the establishment of regional and worldwide economic organizations. (R. Abilasha and M. Ilankumaran 2018). According to a recent United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) report, "employers want students to be trained according to the needs of the workplace and want to get rid of subject areas that are meaningless to the necessities of the world of work, and scholars agree that certain reforms are necessary, but emphasize that these adjustments must weigh the requirements of industry against the needs of civil society advancement." (I. Maharsi 2016)." Tan

and Nouvelle also remind us that "higher education is increasingly being considered as crucial to national plans for acquiring shares in the global market, and universities as reservoirs of vital human capital to assist national growth".

In reality, employers evaluate newly hired graduates' professional competence, even if it is the key criteria for educational success. (M. Ilankumaran and P. Deepa 2018). With the foregoing in mind, and as far as everyone is concerned, a large number of recent research and educations have focused on graduate employability and professional competence (such as critical thinking, problem-solving, leadership, and teamwork skills) rather than communication abilities in English required and used in the real workplace. However, the aforementioned concept appears to be inappropriate for preparing English primary graduates for future professions, particularly those who are not native English speakers. It's logical to assume that after they finish their degree, they'll pursue occupations that require them to use the English language. (G. Charyulu 2015). As a result, it is clear that graduates' English communication skills are critical and highly valued by businesses and organizations. As a result, universities and academic institutions are likely to place a larger emphasis on professional competencies and employability skills.

Letters, phrases, words, sentences, essays, paragraphs, and stories are some of the items that make up literature. When studying a language, the author should focus on all of these knowledge areas. Communication includes the exchange of ideas, opinions, feelings, and facts with people for either professional or personal reasons. (M. Ilankumaran and P. Deepa 2018). Literature is the core of language and the mind. The lexicographical, grammatical, and syntactical systems that comprise language. Anyone looking to improve their communication skills should focus on language. In general, there are three types of communication. (S. Kuroda and I. Yamamoto 2018).

- Visual communication
- Verbal communication
- Auditory communication

In professional communication, the author requires stronger verbal communication skills than visual and oral communication. The author focuses on literature rather than raw, lifeless phrases as grammar models to help us improve our English. One must concentrate on the essential concepts of the language. Focus first on the alphabet, short word lists, word groupings, sentences, phrases, and story paragraphs. (M. S. Kaper 2018). Telling mythical, mystical, or legendary stories helps you improve your linguistic skills. Stories are the most effective technique to strengthen analytical and cognitive skills. Stories provide ample opportunities for the creative process to grow. People used to hone their linguistic talents by listening to legendary stories and telling them to others. However, stories are no longer part of the academic curriculum, and young people are unaware of the value of literature. Even parents think fiction is a pleasant way to spend time. It is meaningless. It's a misconception. Only by reading and listening to literature can we develop our command of the English language and our communication skills. (A. V. Basantes, M. E. Naranjo, M. C. Gallegos, and N. M. Benítez 2017).

The internet has created new opportunities for knowledge advancement through communication. We cannot divorce the Internet from English. They have mingled. Modern technology has created a Digital World in which people may connect swiftly using email, chat, video conferencing, mobile interviewing, net banking, and online buying, among other techniques. Today, man exists within a digital environment. (P. Deepa and M. Ilankumaran 2018). His requirements are for cutting-edge technologies. Computer technology and the English language are two of the most significant tools for connecting the world. These are effective technological and communication tools. Nowadays, technological communication skills are necessary in the

economic, educational, and professional fields. Everyone used to be different, but now we're all known as global citizens. Students have become global citizens, and their jobs have become global occupations. Nowadays, if an educated individual does not know English or how to use a computer, he is regarded to as illiterate. (M. Reza Ahmadi, H. Nizam Ismail, and M.KamarulKabilan Abdullah 2013).

The primary role of a language is to be spoken rather than written. Thus, written languages are the most significant resource for retracing the cultures, societies, and lifestyles of previous generations of individuals and races. (S. Shrestha, S.Parajuli, and U. R. Paudel 2019). The English language is never stagnant; it is always extending into new realms and concepts. (K. B. HaskardZolnierrek and M. R. Dimatteo 2009). The Anglo-Saxon language had only about 20,000 words in its repertoire. The present Oxford Dictionary has around 4,000,000 terms. The Anglo-Saxons inherited the majority of their language from their German forefathers. Any living language, such as English, has a broad vocabulary and facilitates the study of new concepts, people, and areas. The ancient world had lost its feeling of identity. (B. Crosbie, M. Ferguson, G. Wong, D. M. Walker, S. Vanhegan, and T. Dening 2019).

The printed word was given individuality. So much prose appeared all across the world, including print books, magazines, newspapers, and literature. The printing press connected the entire world through written literature. For millennia, individuals have shared their knowledge and experience via newspapers and books. The novel innovation of man's natural mind resulted in the development of the Computer, an artificial mind. The second breakthrough, the computer, transformed the entire cosmos into a ball. (V. Hoel, C. M. Feunou, and K. Wolf-Ostermann 2021). This occurred as a result of the Internet. On this planet, a new ready-made world existed. When a large world shrinks into a small one, new wants and requirements emerge. The internet is a communication and knowledge tool. Only the English language allows for global communication. Whether it's e-commerce, call centres, software, or professional teachers, the global employment market has something for everyone. The ability to communicate in English is required. Exposure to the outside world with adequate vision is the best way to improve once communication (W.Weng, S. Smk, S. Paul, and K. Osman 2018)

It was first employed during the British government's control. individuals write and speak Telugu, and individuals in other states speak and write in their native languages; in fact, our country was divided based on linguistic differences. Our mother tongue is employed in our everyday communications. Only our language enables us to express our thoughts, ideas, and emotions. As a result, the mother tongue's influence dominates our capacity to communicate fluently and successfully in English. (M. C. Paretti, A. Eriksson, and M. Gustafsson 2019). Because we were not born in the English nation or culture, we are unable to speak English in the manner of an Englishman. Rather than wasting time and energy imitating the English nation and dialect, aim to speak English quickly and flawlessly in order to communicate with the rest of the world.

2. ROLE OF ENGLISH GRAMMAR TO ENHANCE COMMUNICATION

Grammar is an essential component of effective English learning. Grammar plays a critical role in written communication. To write excellent English, one must comprehend the rules of grammar. To develop in their careers, professional graduate students must be able to write effective English. Because the world has changed dramatically, English grammar must adapt. Indian students struggle to follow various language laws and restrictions. The Greek and Latin Classical Languages gave birth to the English Lexicon and its structure. The rules of British English haven't evolved in a long time. As a result, the Global Student searches for options. New technologies, such as the Internet and e-mail, offer him a new path to English mastery. (G. Papanastasiou, A. Drigas, C. Skianis, M.Lytras, and E. Papanastasiou 2019). Even so, English

teachers and textbooks continue to employ age-old English spelling, word order, punctuation, and grammatical norms (K. Bombeke 2012). Students interested in technology seek reality and are willing to learn. Because of their excellent IQ scores. So it's time to modify English grammar with cutting-edge technology; else, grammar would be limited to English textbooks and English instructors' surnames.

Our Prehistoric Civilization has bestowed a magnificent gift onto us. It is written in Sanskrit. It has become drowned in the Global World due to its Conventional Grammatical Rules. The threat to the British English languages comes not from people, but modern communication technology. Sanskrit, Greek, and Latin, the world's three Classical Languages, have all but perished due to their Conventional Lexicon and Grammar (K. S. Juma, D. M. A. Raihan, and D. C. K. Clement 2021).

Need of English Language: During the British administration, Macaulay introduced English to our educational system. Since then, English has been an intrinsic part of our culture. It is an essential commodity in the domains of business, commerce, education, and labor. In India, the British Empire has collapsed, but the English Empire has thrived. During the American Revolution, leaders and citizens devised anti-English slogans, arguing that it should be prohibited. Its adaptability, rather than its structure, is what allows it to continue to thrive. These two terms cannot be distinguished; they are synonyms. Globalization gave rise to the new world. Computer technology and the English language are two basic components that connect the entire world. (D. Khashimova, N. Niyazova, U. Nasirova, D. Israilova, N. Khikmatov, and S. Fayziev 2021). These are effective technological and communication tools. Students have become global students, and their careers have become worldwide jobs.

The most crucial talent is listening. Unfortunately, it is the one that receives the least attention. In our daily lives, we prefer to hear people rather than listen to them. Hearing and listening are two very different things. Hearing is a physical activity, whereas listening is a mental one. We exhibit interest in the other person's body language, as well as his thoughts and ideas when we listen to them. When we are listening to someone, we should keep eye contact with them and not interrupt them while they are speaking to us. Listening is a strong skill for obtaining precise information as well as learning more quickly and efficiently. Around the world, the finest leaders and people are the best listeners. 90 per cent listening and 10% speaking is regarded as the finest communication in terms of successful communication. Skills in Public Speaking: Speech is a centuries-old mode of communication.

The speech was developed by ancient man to communicate his feelings, thoughts, views, and information to others. Speech is a powerful method for sharing information with others and receiving an immediate reaction from the listener. It's a real-time communication system. We communicate with others in a variety of ways. Face-to-face communication is the most effective of all. We obtain a speedy reaction from the receiver in a face-to-face encounter. Speaking with more than two persons is the second way of communication. It's known as a group discussion, role-play, or group dynamics. With this approach, we share our information with a group at a time. The author gets a quick response from the listeners in group conversations as opposed to face-to-face conversations (K. E. Sawarynski, D. M. Baxa, and R. Folberg 2019) "Public Speaking" is a different type of speech. In public speaking, a speaker addresses a large group of people on a certain topic. The speaker and his or her information are given first attention in this procedure. Electronic communication is another mode of communication. This method includes using cell phones, voice mails, e-mails, and chatting. Any type of communication is solely to share information with others. It is the most alive and effective kind of communication compared to other forms of communication. "Reading makes a man perfect," says one author. It's a common phrase used to emphasize the necessity of good reading abilities. What motivates us to read? The basic goal of reading is to understand the meaning of each paragraph in a book. We simply read books to gather information and knowledge. As a result, books are the

future generations' treasures of ancient man's wisdom. There are several sorts of books. Reading may be done in a variety of ways, including word-to-word reading, skimming, and scanning. These are the several methods for reading a book. The author looks through a paragraph to see what information or concept we're seeking for using this strategy. It's all about looking for something in a book rather than learning everything there is to know about that book.

These are the several methods for reading a book. To strengthen your ability to provoke thinking, try reading at least a paragraph every day. Another advantage of reading is that it improves your vocabulary and linguistic skills. Individuals' thoughts, clarity, and meaning increase as a result of reading. Writing Ability: "Writing creates a precise guy." Among the three talents of listening, speaking, and reading, writing is the most challenging. It is a thought-provoking activity. It is an everlasting document. Stones were used to writing on in ancient times. Lithography was the name of the process. They later began writing on animal hides. Later, the Chinese created paper. After a few years, Guttenberg devised the printing press, which revolutionized the writing system. Newspapers, periodicals, and many types of printed books were created.

Reading, Writing, Listening, and Speaking are the four forms of communication that we must master to communicate effectively. And I feel that if we read more, we will be able to enhance our writing, listening, and speaking skills. I'm sure we all do a lot of reading for work. Reading literature that is not immediately relevant to our profession, however, is also necessary, in my opinion. Reading books on numerous themes helps one's general knowledge, imagination, and creativity, among other things, in addition to vocabulary and grammar. These advantages can also aid in bridging gaps between team members from various countries in dispersed teams. It's not simple to get into the habit of reading since we're continually catching up with our fast-paced and chaotic lifestyles.

part from professional competency and employability skills, academic institutions should emphasize and teach workplace communication skills in English to boost English major graduates' capabilities and capacities to satisfy labour market expectations and requirements. As a result, university language programs must be designed to provide appropriate practice in listening, speaking, reading, and writing abilities. These abilities are equally vital, and students typically practice them in different combinations or all at once." "Effort should be made to ensure that what is taught in the course is related to authentic office situations to ensure that the students' professional communication skills are practiced according to the requirements of employers, and match the requirements of employers," the same researchers added. || Every literary person is aware of the concepts of language and literature. They are, nevertheless, the most popular way to acquire language. The importance of literature in the language classroom cannot be overstated. It not only entertains readers but also helps them gain experience and develop critical thinking skills.

Literature also includes a variety of literary forms such as prose, poetry, theatre, book, short tales, and so on. Poetry is the most engaging genre in literature, even though it comes in a variety of forms. Poetry, like the ebb and flow of an ocean, can be works of immense beauty due to its metre and rhyme system. This aids the pupil in demonstrating a greater interest in poetry. On the other side, pupils can use the lines of the poetry to learn more vocabulary. Students gain greater benefits from learning new phrases and vocabulary by using diverse terms of poetry in the classroom.

English is the world's most widely spoken language and is regarded as a crucial language in the United Kingdom. It is regarded as the queen of languages and serves as the official language of the United Kingdom. Furthermore, the English language is gaining ground in all other regional languages. English is the most widely used language in the world. It also occupies a key position in the educational system. The ability to communicate in the target language is regarded as a passport to work. Following India's

independence, several debates arose about the English language's status in the country. Some politicians claimed that English should be eradicated, while others advocated for its continued existence in India.

"It has put a terrible burden on Indian pupils and made us mimics," Mahatma Gandhi observed. The English language is crucial for assimilating libertarian ideals and increasing thinking correctness." In several sectors, English is the most widely used language. As a result, one must be fluent in the English language, and learners must gain communication skills via pragmatism. The primary goal of language instruction should be to improve communicative proficiency. Human communication is unrivalled in its wide use of language via abilities. Communication is beneficial to all of humanity in a variety of ways.

3. DISCUSSION

Both literary and linguistic talents are valued equally in English Literature and Communications degrees. The curriculum aims to teach students how to critically connect with a variety of genres through a variety of texts from across the world. The communicative English graduating curriculum also prepares them to be sensitive to a variety of social circumstances as well as various cultural and literary traditions. When you go through the curriculum, you'll see that, in addition to English literature, you'll learn about mass media communication, journalism, philosophy, travel, and tourism. This one meal contains a lot of variety. It also attempts to provide pupils with the chance to improve their communication abilities. While the courses include a broad range of skills for particular corporate and creative areas such as advertising, business, and public service, they also aim to prepare students for further education in the field. The program's overall goal is to develop autonomous learners with the creative, critical, and analytical abilities needed for lifelong learning.

Important About Communication Skills:

Some pundits expected that the website would herald at the end of human written correspondence, but the reality is very different. Texting, social networks, and email are all becoming increasingly popular forms of communication. Misunderstandings are more likely when there is more communication. Take into account the multiplying effect of social media. With a few clicks, what you used to say to only a few people may suddenly be broadcast to hundreds of millions. In this paper, author discuss why English communication skills are so crucial, as well as some recommendations for meeting today's communication needs, whether English is your first language or you're studying it as a second. You'll also learn about how National University can assist you in improving your English abilities through our ESOL (English speakers of other languages) programs or our English and communication degree options.

Important About English:

The term "lingua franca" refers to a language that serves as a "bridge" language. When two individuals who speak different non-English languages meet, English is frequently the language they use to communicate. This is why English is taught in many schools across the world, and many worldwide businesses have made it mandatory for staff in all regions to communicate in English.

English is the most widely used navigational language, such as among air traffic controllers and airline pilots, and it is also the most widely used language on the internet. It is one of the United Nation's six official languages, with 193 members. It is also the language of scientific study, with English being used in 96 per cent of science journals. Some researchers claim that mastering English communication is just as vital as their thesis in acquiring their Doctor of Philosophy (PhD).

Today, around 2 billion people speak English. English is the third most spoken language in the world, although it is the first language learnt by speakers of other languages. In reality, more people communicate in

English as a second language than in their original tongue. Whether you began studying English communication as a child or much later, being able to successfully use English language skills is a significant benefit, particularly in the business.

Communication is a commonplace social action that is a necessary and natural part of being human. This article focuses on how literature in general, and poetry in particular, helps pupils improve their communication abilities. Every literary person is aware of the concepts of language and literature. They are, nevertheless, the most popular way to acquire language. The importance of literature in the language classroom cannot be overstated. It not only entertains readers but also helps them gain experience and develop critical thinking skills.

Literature also includes a variety of literary forms like prose, poetry, theatre, book, short tales, and so on. Poetry is the most engaging genre in literature, even though it comes in a variety of forms. Poetry, like the retreat and flow of an ocean, can be a work of immense beauty due to its metre and rhyme system. This aids the pupil in demonstrating a greater interest in poetry. On the other side, pupils can use the lines of the poetry to learn more vocabulary. Students gain greater benefits from learning new phrases and vocabulary by using diverse terms of poetry in the classroom.

The term communication is one of the most analysed terms in the academic arena and it has been studied systematically since ancient times. Communication is an everyday social activity that is an essential and inherent component of every human being. It is a key to human development because the quality of the existence is linked directly to the quality of the communication. This article focuses on how literature in general and poetry in particular

enhances the communication skills of the students. Every literary person knows about language and literature. However, they are most common to learn the vocabulary. Literature plays a key role in language classroom. It provides not only pleasure to readers but also builds experience and creates thinking ability. Moreover, literature has several literary forms such as prose, poetry, drama, novel, short stories, etc. Though there are several forms in literature, the most interesting genre is poetry. Poetry can be the works of great beauty due to its meter and rhyme scheme like the ebb and flow of an ocean. This really helps the student to show more involvement towards poetry. On the other hand, the students can try to know more vocabulary from the lines of the poems. Through different terms of poetry used in the classroom, the students get more benefits of knowing new terms and words.

4. CONCLUSION

The prose is the most effective instrument for learning English and Prose has built-in grammar. As a result, students may quickly learn Prose Topics. Words, nouns, verbs, punctuation, phrases, and sentences make up prose. Grammar should be taught in conjunction with Prose Paragraphs rather than individually. Students study Grammatical Assemblies in a highly efficient manner. Prose instruction nowadays is mechanical and serves no use. But it serves a greater purpose than simply explaining and translating it. Mathematical Applications are analogous to English Language Prose. Every single word and sentence is true and correct. As a result, it should not be squandered by translating. If a student masters prose, he will naturally master English communication skills. Professionals that are fluent in English are in high demand in today's job market. The four regions of English should be learned to gain command of the language. Listening, Reading, Speaking, and Writing is the four branches of the English language. These four abilities are referred to as communication skills. Speech is more significant than writing in language learning. The author uses Spoken

Language to share our opinions regularly. To talk successfully, students need to master basic grammar rules and this rule help for better future communication skills.

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